

CODE OF CONDUCT AND ETHICAL STANDARDS FOR PUBLIC OFFICIALS AND EMPLOYEES (RA6713) IN THE MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENT, PROVINCE OF RIZAL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to assess the Municipal Government of Rizal's adherence to Republic Act 6713, often referred to as the Public Employees' Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards. The municipalities in the eastern area of Rizal were the sites of this. The permanent employees and stakeholders of the seven municipalities make up the responders. The towns of Jala-jala, Pililla, Tanay, Baras, Morong, Cardona, and Teresa are the ones that are being surveyed. 61 stakeholders and 370 regular municipal employees made up a total of 431 responses. In contrast to other typical studies that have been done in the past and have linked RA 6713 to job performance, the goal of this study is to determine the level of confidence that stakeholders have for employees in order to promote G2P (government-to-person) collaboration. The descriptive technique of research was employed in the current study. This kind of research design is used to describe a condition or phenomenon. It entails gathering information using questionnaires, interviews, surveys, and observations. Descriptive research seeks to give a precise and in-depth account of a certain group, event, or circumstance. Finding patterns, trends, and linkages in the data can be aided by it (Hassan, 2024). The research employed a self-made, properly validated instrument that comprised the respondent profile and respondent-rated items covering eight areas of RA 6713. The collected data was then subjected to statistical processing, assessment, and analysis. The study's findings showed that, of the eight categories, the employees' ratings were consistent, contrary to the stakeholders'.

Keywords: *Ethics, Trust, Stakeholders, Code of Conduct, Transparency*

INTRODUCTION

Growing incidences of indulgence of employees in unethical acts in various organizations and negative consequences associated with it for the organization such as erosion of reputation because of advanced digital media coverage, shareholder value, and others made it compulsive to study the root cause of unethical behavior at the workplace (Jha and Singh, 2021). The most generally accepted concept of Ethics is that culture is a key determinant of an individual's ethical ideology (Onder, et al, 2020) To be an ethical person is simply to know what is right and wrong. Ethics are often explained by the Golden Rule, which says, "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you." But morality and ethics are two different concepts. According to Wheeler's paper, "individual value choices are the key to implementing an organizational culture that does not tolerate unethical behavior." Furthermore, the collection of rules that professionals in a certain sector must adhere to is known as the ethical standard or code of ethics in that profession.

It seems like more businesses are making an effort to adopt a code of conduct and grow more accountable. The code of conduct currently establishes the parameters that businesses and governments must operate within. All levels of management and staff will be held to the standard established by the actions of the top leader. At the director level, ethical behavior must begin. The department must be dedicated to addressing ethical concerns and not be in the habit of hiding anything from the public during the decision-making process. It all boils down to good intentions. People will detect an ethical aim if it is genuine.

The creation and continuing revision of a code of ethics is part of the natural development of any profession. A code of ethics is a living document that changes as the profession grows and changes. This evolution is reflected in the successive iterations of our ethical standards, which have existed for more than fifty years (Herlihy & Corey, 2015). A code of ethics is something that naturally forms and is constantly modified in any profession. A code of ethics is a living document that changes as the field does. Over the course of more than 50 years, our ethical standards have undergone several revisions to reflect this advancement.

The current study aimed to address the concerns of the stakeholders with reference to the subscription of employees over RA 6713 to harmonize trust and encourage the former in the participation of municipal government affairs, hence yielding to a Government-to-person mutual agreement.

Ethics is more accurately the study of such societal codes and morals concerning how they impact society. In essence, ethics encompasses how moral concepts affect the larger society in which they are employed. The study of ethics is more concerned with how human interaction impacts the ability of the greater society to function. While

many ethical actions are also considered moral in most cultures, it is possible to have an ethical action that is immoral or an amoral action that is unethical, depending on how a specific culture defines its moral code. Moral judgments are often based on adherence to pre-defined codes of conduct, whereas ethical judgments are based on determining how a course of action may impact things and the people around them. Thus, the trust of the people heightened if civil servants performed their tasks without reservations, favoritism, and impartiality. Therefore, ethics are the set of guidelines that specify how public servants should behave to guarantee that the public is treated fairly and equally. Ethics assist public servants in making better decisions that serve the public interest and assist the public in assessing the decisions made by public servants on their behalf.

The nation has the strictest ethical standards in the world, as required by RA 6713 (Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees),

and has the highest ethical requirements in the nation. In terms of dedication to the public interest, professionalism, fairness and sincerity, political neutrality, public responsiveness, nationalism, patriotism, dedication to democracy, and simple living, the current study evaluated the degree of work ethics practiced by government employees. (https://www.ombudsman.gov.ph/docs/republicacts/Republic_Act_No_6713).

Ordinarily, elections are held on the second Monday of May, as required by the Philippine Constitution. This is regarded as a forum for citizens to engage in government affairs; therefore, if the municipal government and interested parties mutually agree, there may be additional involvement for stakeholders beyond voting.

In conclusion, code of conduct and ethical standards in the government are essential for maintaining public trust, ensuring transparency, and promoting accountability. They serve as the foundation for good governance, guiding officials in making decisions that prioritize the public interest over personal gain. High ethical standards help prevent corruption, foster a culture of integrity, and enhance the credibility of governmental institutions. Ultimately, adherence to ethical principles is crucial for the effective functioning of democracy, as it ensures that the actions of government officials align with the values and expectations of the society they serve. Therefore, to address problems encountered by both groups of respondents an action plan thereby proposed.

Research Questions

The current study aimed to assess how the ethical standard is being subscribed by every employee in the local government unit in the Eastern Province of Rizal. Specifically, it attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 municipality
 - 1.2 sex
 - 1.3 age

- 1.4 educational attainment
 - 1.5 length of service (for employees)
 2. How do RA 6713 subscribe by the municipal employees in the province of Rizal as perceived by the respondents with respect to:
 - 2.1 commitment to public interest
 - 2.2 professionalism
 - 2.3 justness and sincerity
 - 2.4 political neutrality
 - 2.5 responsiveness
 - 2.6 nationalism and patriotism
 - 2.7 commitment to democracy; and
 - 2.8 simple living
 3. Is there a significant difference in the subscription of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to the cited variables in terms of their profile?
 4. What may be the problems encountered by the respondents in the implementation of RA 6713?
 5. What solutions may be proposed based on the problems encountered?
 6. What plan of action may be designed to strengthen the implementation of RA 6713 in the municipalities of the 2nd district of Rizal?
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METHODOLOGY

To give justification on how the conduct of this study materialized, this chapter presents the method of research, population, sampling technique, description of the respondents, instrumentation, procedures in data-gathering, and statistical treatment that will be used.

Method of Research

The researcher utilized the descriptive method of research by using a three-part survey questionnaire that assessed the implementation of a code of ethical standards for public employees in the Province of Rizal.

The descriptive method research approach is used to describe systematically and accurately the facts and characteristics of a given population or area of interest. Hence, it is significant in the current conduct of the study.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

To draw a reliable response, this study involved the permanent employees in the seven (7) municipalities in eastern Rizal that is, Tanay, Pililla and Jalajala, Baras, Morong, Cardona, and Teresa. the other group of respondents was chosen through convenient sampling. Of the total number of permanent employees in the municipalities in Eastern Rizal consisting of Eight Hundred Twenty-One (821), there were Three Hundred Seventy responded. For the other group of respondents who were chosen through convenient sampling, sixty-one (61) answered.

Description of Respondents

The respondents utilized in this study were the 370 permanent employees of the municipalities in the eastern part of Rizal and 61 stakeholders, they were described based on their demographic profile that includes municipality-were majority of the are residents of Tanay, sex-were majority are female, age whose highest frequency were those ages 46-50, highest educational attainment-were college graduate outnumbered other levels, and length of service for the employees-on which 5 years and below is the highest.

Municipality	Total Number of Permanent Employees	Actual Number of Employee-Respondents	Total Number of Stakeholder-Respondents
Baras	71	24	8
Cardona	78	72	5
Jala-jala	72	58	10
Morong	113	37	5
Pililla	156	61	14
Tanay	218	86	12
Teresa	113	29	7
No Answer		3	
TOTAL		370	61

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a self-made instrument that was subjected to content validation. The instrument consists of two parts, the first part includes the demographic profile of the respondents, and the second part consists of a questionnaire divided into eight (8) areas- namely Commitment to Public Interest; Professionalism; Justness and Sincerity; Political Neutrality; Responsiveness to the Public; Nationalism and Patriotism; Commitment to Democracy; and Simple Living. The instrument consists of five items per area and will be rated using a 5-point Likert scale as follows:

Range		Verbal Interpretation
5	-	Very Much Subscribe
4	-	Much Subscribe
3	-	Less Subscribe
2	-	Least Subscribe
1	-	Never Subscribe

Data-gathering Procedure

To arrive at a precise response, the researcher sought approval through a letter to the seven municipalities addressed to the Municipal Mayors through their respective Human Resource Management Officers for their employees to be permitted to participate in the study.

The instrument was distributed to the two groups of respondents and retrieved where results were tallied, evaluated, and interpreted congruent to the statement of the problem.

In terms of retrieving responses from the employees of some municipalities, there was some hesitation in answering the instrument- as stated they are worried that once they responded, and their answers do not appear favorable to the administration, they may be transferred to the office they do not fit, considering that there were incumbent mayors who lost in the then just concluded elections. For the stakeholders, the limited number of respondents was due to the reason that the study was conducted during the pandemic and most of the services were transacted online or electronically, henceforth despite several attempts of going to the municipalities the least that was considered was providing Google forms to the frontline service providers of each municipality and some nearby government institutions within the area.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

To properly analyze and interpret the problems, the following statistical tools were utilized;

For Problem Number 1 and 4, Frequency and Percentage distribution were utilized to provide data on the profile of the respondents.

For Problem Number 2, Weighted Mean was used to assess the subscription of the Municipal in terms of variables.

For Problem Number 3, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate the significant difference of the respondents in terms of profile with respect to the variables.

RESULTS

This following deals with the Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of the results based on the gathered data of the current study.

Table 1 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Municipality

Municipality	f	%	Rank
Baras	32	7.4	7
Cardona	77	17.9	2
Jalajala	68	15.8	4
Morong	42	9.7	5
Piñilla	75	17.4	3
Tanay	98	22.7	1
Teresa	36	8.4	6
No Answer	3	.7	
Total	431	100.0	

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of Municipality. According to the number of respondents per municipality, Tanay ranked highest with 98 total respondents, or 22.7 percent, followed by Cardona with 77 total respondents, or 17.9 percent, and Baras has the least with 32 total respondents or 7.4 percent.

The results implied that majority of employees of the government are residing from the municipality of Tanay. In addition, Tanay has the largest population in the 2020 Statistical Data of Population (Atlas, 2020) among the mentioned municipalities above, reason why there are government employees employed in Tanay. Moreover, because of the big population, Tanay have the overall system and service of the government to the public.

Table 2 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	f	%	Rank
Male	158	36.7	2
Female	262	60.8	1
No Answer	11	2.6	
Total	431	100.0	

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of Sex, which shows that the majority of the respondents are female with a frequency of 262 or 60.8 percent, on the other hand, males are 158 or 36.7 percent.

The results indicate that there are more female government employees in the municipality of Tanay. The result also implied that there is a share and equal amount of women in government employment which is an implication of openness and fairness in public sector (OECD, 2013).

Table 3 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	f	%	Rank
25 years old and below	49	11.4	5
26-30 years old	52	12.1	4
31-35 years old	46	10.7	7
36-40 years old	31	7.2	8
41-45 years old	47	10.9	6
46-50 years old	65	15.1	1
51-55 years old	55	12.8	3
56 years old and above	62	14.4	2
No Answer	24	5.6	9
Total	431	100.0	

As presented in Table, it was revealed that in terms of age, the majority of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 46-50 years old followed by those ages 56 years old and above, while those who belong to the age bracket of 36-40 got the least.

The results implied that majority of government employees in Tanay are middle aged. There are more middle aged employees because of several reasons, one is that in the public sector government jobs are in occupations requiring specialized training, education or job skills compared to private sector (OECD, 2017).

Table 4 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	f	%	Rank
High School Level	2	.5	10
High School Graduate	9	2.1	4.5
College Level	34	7.9	2
College Graduate	295	68.4	1
Masteral Level	5	1.2	7.5
Masters Graduate	23	5.3	3
Vocational	9	2.1	4.5
Doctoral Degree	6	1.4	6
Senior High School Graduate	5	1.2	7.5
Post Graduate	4	.9	9
With Units in Doctorate	1	.2	11
No Answer	38	8.8	
Total	431	100.0	

Table 4 provides the number of respondents in terms of educational attainment and discloses that college graduate has the most number of 295 or 68.4 percent, followed by those who gained college-level with a frequency of 34 or 7.9 percent, and those with units in Doctorate has the least number of 1 or .2 percent.

The results implied that government employees have finished and obtained a Bachelor’s Degree which is obvious and understandable because it is the minimum requirement in applying in public sector. According to RULE VIII “QUALIFICATION STANDARD“ Part I. General Policies Sec. 31. The qualification standards are the minimum and basic requirements for positions in the government in terms of education, training, experience, Civil Service eligibility, physical fitness and other qualities required for successful performance of the duties of the position. These shall serve as the basic guide in the selection of the employees and in the evaluation of appointments to all positions in the government (CSC, 2017 Omnibus Rules on Appointments and Other Human Resource Actions). With above mentioned qualifications, having a degree is essential most especially in the government.

Table 5 Profile of the Employees in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service (Employees)	f	%	Rank
5 years and below	103	27.8	1
6-10 years	59	15.9	3
11-15 years	54	14.6	4
16-20 years	43	11.6	6
21 years and above	62	16.8	2
No Answer	49	13.2	5
Total	370	100.0	

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of length of service. It was revealed that those who have been connected in the municipality within the last five years have the highest number with a frequency of 103 or 27.8 percent, on the contrary employees who have been serving the municipality for 16-20 years with a frequency of 43 or 11.6 percent were the least.

The results implied that majority of the employees are considered as Casual employees with less or five (5) years of government service (Republic Act no. 6656 - an Act to Protect the Security of Tenure of Civil Service Officers and employees in the implementation of Government Reorganization - Supreme Court E-Library). In addition, length of service is important for the government because it can indicate the quality of an employee. It shows that an employee has been successfully working in the organization for a long period of time and may have developed specific skillsets or knowledge about their role, resulting to a more functional service to the public (Jarvis, 2023).

Table 6 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Category

Category	f	%	Rank
Employee	370	85.8	1
Stakeholder	61	14.2	2
Total	431	100.0	

Table 6 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of category where it depicts that the majority are employees with a frequency of 370 or 85.8 percent while stakeholders got a frequency of 61 or 14.2 percent.

The results indicate that there are more government employees than stakeholder in the government in Eastern part of Rizal province. Government employees are more valuable than ever because they genuinely want a process like this to succeed and have the knowledge and enthusiasm to make sure it does. Band-aid solutions, such as wage freezing, may win popular favor temporarily, but they have a number of unanticipated long-term effects (such as diverting the best and the brightest to the private sector) (December, 2010)

Table 7 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Commitment to Public Interest

Commitment to Public Interest	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Practices free exchange of information and ideas regarding policies and implementations of the municipality	4.51	VM	4.16	M	4.46	VMS
Attends to concerns of clients as prescribed by ARTA (anti-red tape act)	4.47	VM	4.07	M	4.41	VMS
Upholds public interest over and above personal interest.	4.66	VM	4.16	M	4.59	VMS
Perform duties even during times of calamities.	4.64	VM	4.36	VM	4.60	VMS
Provides honest information that concern Public interest	4.76	VM	4.31	VM	4.69	VMS
Average	4.60	VM	4.21	VM	4.55	VMS

Legend: VM- Very Much M-Much

In terms of Commitment to Public Interest, despite that Stakeholders do not have the same rating as that of the employees in items 1-3, the overall verbal interpretation is Very Much.

The results indicates that employees are more committed to served the publics interest's, however, stakeholders are also commit to public interest especially in responding and performing during calamities.

According to the study of M Lennon, the ‘public interest’ has long been used as a concept to justify planning activity, hence expectations from the client or sector should be given optimal consideration, further, it was given highlights the importance of acknowledging how identifying the public interest demands situated ethical judgment (Lennon, 2016).

Table 8 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Professionalism

Professionalism	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Observes official time religiously.	4.64	VM	4.16	M	4.57	VMS
Performs duties and functions with highest degree of excellence	4.73	VM	4.18	M	4.65	VMS
Discourage favors prior to performance of services	4.52	VM	4.00	M	4.44	VMS
Choose appropriate words when dealing to clients	4.80	VM	4.25	VM	4.73	VMS
Observes loyalty in the organization and supports the co-workers	4.75	VM	4.20	VM	4.67	VMS
Average	4.69	VM	4.16	M	4.61	VMS

Table 8 shows that in terms of Professionalism, both groups or respondents have the same assessment with a verbal interpretation of Very Much. However, some areas of Stakeholder have a verbal interpretation of Much which is lower than employee respondents. The results implied that both respondents present professionalism at work and in public service.

As mentioned in the study of Lorilla, it was found that most of the clients experienced the cessation of working hours during lunch break, which they found to be inappropriate since the government issued a “no noon-break” policy in all government offices and agencies. A number of respondents also experienced that the absence of a special lane for persons with disabilities (PWDs) is apparent in most of the offices in the municipal hall.

Furthermore, a significant number of respondents also claimed that they find some employees discourteous or disrespectful towards the clients of the said office, which they are quite aware, that in violation of the law governing the ethics of government employees. Under section 4, paragraph (b) of RA 6713, it was provided that “They shall enter public service with utmost devotion and dedication to duty. They shall endeavor to discourage wrong perceptions of their roles as dispensers or peddlers of undue patronage.” Be as it may, in the course of the study, every single respondent admitted that they did not report any misconduct that they experienced by diverse reasons like lack of time, the arduous process of the complaint, to name a few.

Table 9 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Justness and Sincerity

Justness and Sincerity	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Observe transparency in performing the job/duties	4.82	VM	4.23	VM	4.74	VMS
Avoids giving out favors to relatives whether by affinity or consanguinity	4.56	VM	3.85	M	4.46	VMS
Respect the rights of others	4.84	VM	4.33	VM	4.77	VMS
Executes impartiality in the performance of duties and responsibilities	4.75	VM	4.02	M	4.64	VMS
Accept shortcomings and rectify actions immediately to correct it.	4.73	VM	4.13	M	4.64	VMS
Average	4.74	VM	4.11	M	4.65	VMS

As revealed in Table 9, all the items were rated by the two groups of respondents as Very Much Implemented which implies that in terms of Justness and Sincerity the Municipal Employees subscribed.

To support this, the study of MJ Somers *Ethical Codes of Conduct and Organizational Context* as cited by Franco (2023) The presence of corporate codes of ethics was associated with less perceived wrongdoing in organizations, but not with an increased propensity to report observed unethical behavior. Further, organizations that adopted formal codes of ethics exhibited value orientations that went beyond financial performance to include responsibility to the commonweal. In contrast to corporate codes of ethics, professional codes of ethical conduct had no influence on perceived wrongdoing in the organization nor did these codes affect the propensity to report observed unethical activities.

Table 10 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Political Neutrality

Political Neutrality	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Provide services to everyone without discrimination	4.80	VM	4.18	M	4.71	VMS
Deliver services regardless of party affiliation or preference	4.75	VM	4.02	M	4.65	VMS
Avoids favoring incumbent officials of the municipality	4.56	VM	3.92	M	4.47	VMS
Avoids promotion of elected officials especially during campaign for election	4.57	VM	3.84	M	4.47	VMS
Exercises political rights without considerations to incumbent officials	4.66	VM	3.74	M	4.53	VMS
Average	4.67	VM	3.94	M	4.57	VMS

Table 10 revealed that in terms of subscription to Political Neutrality, Municipal Employees duly pledged to it.

The table presents that in terms of exercising political rights without consideration to incumbent officials, stakeholders ranked it least, which gives an impression that there are employees and/or positions in the municipality that have reference to the incumbent elected officials. Contrary to what was mentioned in the study of Ryzin, it was stated that it is often assumed that citizens evaluate government based on service quality or outcomes (such as safe neighborhoods or good schools), but aspects of administrative process (such as fairness and respect) are also important. Using data from two US surveys, this study examines how service quality and administrative processes influence citizens' evaluations of the government. Results indicate that service quality matters most to ratings of the community; in contrast, the administrative process is the dominant driver of trust; and both quality and process have large effects on judgments about government's overall job performance. Implications for public management research and practice are discussed.

Table 11 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Responsiveness

Responsiveness	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Extends prompt, courteous, and adequate service to the public	4.78	VM	4.28	VM	4.71	VMS
Provides correct information of the policies and procedures in clear and understandable language	4.78	VM	4.31	VM	4.71	VMS
Ensure openness of information, and public hearings whenever appropriate	4.72	VM	4.20	VM	4.64	VMS
Executes immediate actions on the concern of clients	4.75	VM	4.10	M	4.66	VMS
Gives an accurate list of requirements when requesting for documents or other concern	4.75	VM	4.20	VM	4.67	VMS
Average	4.75	VM	4.22	VM	4.68	VMS

Table 11 presents responses from both employees and stakeholders in terms of responsiveness, it was revealed that among five items it was the third that ranked the least, which is *Executes immediate actions on the concern of clients*. Relative to the study of Vigoda, research in public administration (PA) is preoccupied with questions of efficiency and effectiveness which are aimed at improving public sector performance. According to the new public management approach, addressing this prominent challenge must rely upon a comprehensive understanding of citizens'/clients' perceptions of public sector operation and the extent to which public organizations are aware of public needs.

Table 12 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Nationalism and Patriotism

Nationalism and Patriotism	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Attends flag raising and retreat at all times	4.74	VM	4.39	VM	4.69	VMS
Maintain loyalty to the Republic and Filipino people	4.84	VM	4.48	VM	4.79	VMS
Promote the use of locally produced goods, resources and technology and encourage appreciation and pride of country and people	4.59	VM	4.39	VM	4.57	VMS
Subscribe to unity on the development that may be proposed by the Municipality	4.74	VM	4.38	VM	4.68	VMS
Complies to the call of the government especially in of times crises, calamities, and the likes.	4.68	VM	4.39	VM	4.63	VMS
Average	4.72	VM	4.41	VM	4.68	VMS

Table 12 on the previous page presents the subscription of employees to Nationalism and Patriotism which *Maintain loyalty to the Republic and Filipino people*, ranked first to both respondents, while for the stakeholders the least is *Subscribed to unity on the development that may be proposed by the Municipality*, and for the employees, it is *Promote the use of locally produced goods, resources and technology and encourage appreciation and pride of country and people*.

On June 1, 2022, the Civil Service Commission through the Philippine Information Agency issued a “reiterated” on the observance of RA 6713, the CSC head urged government workers, as civil servants, to familiarize themselves with the 1987 Philippine Constitution, the Code of Conduct for public officials and employees, and other laws of the land.

According to the Chair, "as public servants, it is incumbent upon us to be examples of good and responsible citizenship. Further, "he urged them to provide excellent service at all times, without discrimination on the basis of age, gender, economic status, or political affiliation. "Always be mindful that our loyalty lies with the country, and that we are all accountable to our people."

Table 13 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Commitment to Democracy

Table 13 presents the responses of the two groups of respondents with respect to Commitment to Democracy showing that in the item Votes on the scheduled national and local elections, and any other forms of exercising suffrage they have a common

thought. Elections and electoral processes are fundamental to the workings of every democratic setting of the modern state. Elections are the major hallmark of a democratic society. Recognizing this statement from the work of Igbokwe-Ibeto, it implies that in terms of subscribing to democracy both of group groups of respondents are amenable.

Commitment to Democracy	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Commit themselves to the democratic way of life and values	4.63	VM	4.36	VM	4.59	VMS
Maintain the principles of public accountability, and manifest by deeds the supremacy of civilian authority over the military	4.63	VM	4.20	VM	4.57	VMS
Uphold the constitution and put loyalty to the country above loyalty to persons or party	4.66	VM	4.23	VM	4.60	VMS
Votes on the scheduled national and local elections and any other form of exercising suffrage	4.79	VM	4.44	VM	4.74	VMS
Supports the Sangguniang Bayan in all their programs and projects by disseminating it properly to the community	4.71	VM	4.26	VM	4.64	VMS
Average	4.68	VM	4.30	VM	4.63	VMS

Table 14 Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents with respect to Simple Living

Simple Living	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Lead modest lives, including his/her family appropriate to their positions and income	4.70	VM	4.11	M	4.61	VMS
Do not indulge in extravagant or ostentatious display of wealth in any form	4.70	VM	4.02	M	4.60	VMS
Wear of uniforms and avoiding use of excessive accessories	4.69	VM	4.23	VM	4.62	VMS
Shows happiness and contentment in their life by performing their task even additional duties without being forced to	4.69	VM	4.15	M	4.61	VMS
Avoids accepting material things in return of the job performed	4.70	VM	4.15	M	4.62	VMS
Average	4.69	VM	4.13	M	4.61	VMS

As revealed by Table 14, it asserts that on the part of employees, items 1,2, and 5 have the same mean of 4.70, on the contrary for the stakeholders' item 3 got the highest rank. This implies that both groups of respondents affirm that employees exercise simple living regardless of rank or position. This empirically examines the article by Feldheim and Wang on the relationship between administrative ethics and public trust mentioned in the study of Muel Kaptein (2015). A model is developed linking the ethical behaviors of public organizations to citizen trust as perceived by managers. The model is tested with data from a survey of cities in the United States. The results show that there are higher perceptions of trust in cities where there are higher perceptions of ethical behaviors. The study indicates that an effective strategy to improve trust should emphasize honest behavior by employees, encourage employee openness, and promote organizational and individual loyalty to the public interest.

Table 15 Composite Table on the Subscription on the RA6713 by the Municipal Employees in the Province of Rizal as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents

	Employee		Stakeholder		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	4.60	VM	4.21	VM	4.55	VMS
Professionalism	4.69	VM	4.16	M	4.61	VMS
Justness and Sincerity	4.74	VM	4.11	M	4.65	VMS
Political Neutrality	4.67	VM	3.94	M	4.57	VMS
Responsiveness	4.75	VM	4.22	VM	4.68	VMS
Nationalism and Patriotism	4.72	VM	4.41	VM	4.68	VMS
Commitment to Democracy	4.68	VM	4.30	VM	4.63	VMS
Simple Living	4.69	VM	4.13	M	4.61	VMS
Grand Mean	4.70	VM	4.18	M	4.62	VMS

Legend: VM- Very Much M-Much

As shown in table 15, in terms of Professionalism, Justness and Sincerity, Political Neutrality, and Simple Living, the two groups of respondents answered contradictory just as how it was narrated, accordingly, Codes of ethics are being increasingly adopted in organizations worldwide, yet their effects on employee perceptions and behavior have not been thoroughly addressed. Just like a study that used a sample of management accountants drawn from the United States to study the relationship between corporate and professional codes of ethics and employee attitudes and behaviors. The presence of corporate codes of ethics was associated with less perceived wrongdoing in organizations, but not with an increased propensity to report observed unethical behavior. Further, organizations that adopted formal codes of ethics exhibited value orientations that went beyond financial performance to include the responsibility to the commonweal. In contrast to corporate codes of ethics, professional codes of ethical conduct had no influence on perceived wrongdoing in organization nor these codes affect the propensity to report observed unethical activities.

Table 16 on the succeeding page presents the significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of the municipality.

Table 16 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Municipal Employees with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Municipality

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Ho	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	4.585	6	.764	2.985	.007	R	S
	Within Groups	107.523	420	.256				
	Total	112.108	426					
Professionalism	Between Groups	4.688	6	.781	3.302	.003	R	S
	Within Groups	99.630	421	.237				
	Total	104.318	427					
Justness and Sincerity	Between Groups	2.788	6	.465	1.645	.133	FR	NS
	Within Groups	118.656	420	.283				
	Total	121.444	426					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	3.832	6	.639	1.741	.110	FR	NS
	Within Groups	151.897	414	.367				
	Total	155.729	420					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	2.353	6	.392	1.573	.153	FR	NS
	Within Groups	104.711	420	.249				
	Total	107.064	426					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	2.325	6	.388	1.922	.076	FR	NS
	Within Groups	84.705	420	.202				
	Total	87.031	426					
Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	4.486	6	.748	2.864	.010	R	S
	Within Groups	108.599	416	.261				
	Total	113.086	422					
Simple Living	Between Groups	3.421	6	.570	1.742	.110	FR	NS
	Within Groups	137.483	420	.327				
	Total	140.904	426					

Sig. < 0.05 R S Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

It was revealed that there is a significant difference in the Practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest and professionalism in terms of municipality since the computed p-values of .007 and .003

respectively are less than the 0.05 level of significance, hence, the hypothesis is rejected. With respect to justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness and nationalism and patriotism, there is no significant difference since the p-values of .133, .110, .153, and .076 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis. There is significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to democracy in terms of municipality since the p-value of .010 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Lastly, with respect to simple living, there is no significant difference in terms of municipality since the p-value of .110 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, with respect to commitment to democracy, the null hypothesis is rejected, while with respect to simple living, the study failed to reject the hypothesis.

In conclusion of the results above, majority of the cited variables are not significant to the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the Municipal Employees. To support this result, a study from Magtibay and Caballes (2023), the way people related to another is one of the key factors that helps to easily comply with the required job needs to be done, however as the target job failed to comply the human relations somehow affected also within the workplace. Further, better environmental practices can lead to superior quality, and to improve environmental practices, policies may be modified to shape the culture thereby leading to the superior quality of work.

Table 17 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Municipal Employees with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Sex

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Ho	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	2.175	1	2.175	8.287	.004	R	S
	Within Groups	109.465	417	.263				
	Total	111.640	418					
Professionalism	Between Groups	.860	1	.860	3.509	.062	FR	NS
	Within Groups	102.472	418	.245				
	Total	103.332	419					
Justness and Sincerity	Between Groups	.764	1	.764	2.661	.104	FR	NS
	Within Groups	119.795	417	.287				
	Total	120.560	418					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	1.884	1	1.884	5.072	.025	R	S
	Within Groups	152.656	411	.371				
	Total	154.540	412					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	.217	1	.217	.852	.357	FR	NS
	Within Groups	106.362	417	.255				
	Total	106.580	418					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	.521	1	.521	2.530	.112	FR	NS
	Within Groups	85.935	417	.206				
	Total	86.456	418					

Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	1.352	1	1.352	5.043	.025	R	S
	Within Groups	110.478	412	.268				
	Total	111.831	413					
Simple Living	Between Groups	1.128	1	1.128	3.382	.067	FR	NS
	Within Groups	138.801	416	.334				
	Total	139.929	417					

Sig. < 0.05 R S

Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

Table 17 revealed that there is a significant difference in the Practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to the public interest in terms of sex since the computed p-value of .004 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, hence, the hypothesis is rejected.

With respect to professionalism, justness and sincerity, there is no significant difference since the p-values of .062 and .104 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis. With respect to political neutrality, there is a significant difference in terms of sex since the p-value of .025 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There is no significant difference with respect to responsiveness and nationalism and patriotism since the p-values of .357 and .112 are greater than the 0.05 level of significance, therefore the study failed to reject the hypothesis. There is a significant difference in the Practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to democracy in terms of sex since the computed p-value of .025 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Lastly, with respect to simple living, there is no significance since the p-values of .067 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

These result implied that majority of the variables are not connected or have a relationship with the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the Municipal Employees. In relation with this, a study of Amit K. Nandkeolyar, 2022, it was revealed that gender discrimination in the workplace remains a significant challenge for organizations worldwide. Despite some advances in gender equality, researchers have concluded that women are still likely to earn less and lose out on promotions to higher positions compared to men. Sizeable literature supports that gender-based role incongruity and stereotypes can lead to differences in performance evaluations across occupations, job levels, and industries, including highly specialized scientific fields.

However, in some other cases, sex may influence and affects on ratings on measures of ethical decision-making, especially in the government. According to Yang et al. (2016), women rated themselves as more ethical than did men; however, this sex effect on ethical decision-making was no longer significant when social desirability response bias was controlled.

Table 18 presents the significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of age.

The table revealed that there is no significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and

simple living in terms of age since the computed p-values of .421, .244, .276, .697, .162, .186, .351., and .470 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

According to the study of Zaneta Balazova, 2015, Motivation can be changed significantly in dependence on meeting human needs, life situations, internal and external environment, etc. It is caused by different factors which affect motivation in different ways. These factors do not act separately but they are a part of a mutually connected network of specific relations. In the paper, it was shown the possibility of the impact of age, education, and seniority on the motivation of employees. The level of employee motivation and employee performance can be influenced by means of their detailed knowledge.

Table 18 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Municipal Employees with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Age

	SV	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig.	Ho	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	1.876	7	.268	1.014	.421	FR	NS
	Within Groups	105.201	398	.264				
	Total	107.077	405					
Professionalism	Between Groups	2.234	7	.319	1.310	.244	FR	NS
	Within Groups	97.241	399	.244				
	Total	99.475	406					
Justness and Sincerity	Between Groups	2.505	7	.358	1.246	.276	FR	NS
	Within Groups	114.293	398	.287				
	Total	116.798	405					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	1.780	7	.254	.671	.697	FR	NS
	Within Groups	148.589	392	.379				
	Total	150.370	399					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	2.597	7	.371	1.510	.162	FR	NS
	Within Groups	97.780	398	.246				
	Total	100.377	405					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	2.023	7	.289	1.445	.186	FR	NS
	Within Groups	79.590	398	.200				
	Total	81.612	405					
Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	2.016	7	.288	1.118	.351	FR	NS
	Within Groups	101.234	393	.258				
	Total	103.250	400					
Simple Living	Between Groups	2.197	7	.314	.947	.470	FR	NS
	Within Groups	131.635	397	.332				

	Total	133.832	404					
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Sig. < 0.05 R S Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

Table 19 on the succeeding page presents the significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of highest educational attainment.

The table revealed that there is no significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, and, justness and sincerity in terms of highest educational attainment since the computed p-values of .348, .158, and respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to reject the null

hypothesis. With respect to political neutrality and responsiveness, there is a significant difference since the p-values of .011 and .003 respectively are less than 0.5 level of significance, therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. There is no significant difference in terms of nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living since the computed p-values of .208, .314, and .090 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence the study failed to reject the hypothesis Dennis Thompson argues that such officials need to do more than oversee the paperwork associated with ethics legislation and the enforcement of specific standards and rules. They also have an "educational responsibility" in reminding public officials of their role in American democracy. Carrying out this "education in democracy" function is difficult, however, because of three paradoxes or misconceptions that plague the work of ethics officials. These include misconceptions surrounding the relative importance of ethical issues, the conflict between public and private ethical behavior, and the importance of appearances. Thompson discusses each of these paradoxes and the need to get beyond them. The major role for ethics officials, he concludes, is involvement in a continuous, positive, and visible effort to educate government employees about their democratic responsibilities.

Table 19 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Municipal Employees with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Ho	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	2.928	10	.293	1.117	.348	FR	NS
	Within Groups	99.902	381	.262				
	Total	102.830	391					
Professionalism	Between Groups	3.428	10	.343	1.445	.158	FR	NS
	Within Groups	90.605	382	.237				
	Total	94.033	392					
	Between Groups	4.879	10	.488	1.743	.070	FR	NS

Justness and Sincerity	Within Groups	106.675	381	.280				
	Total	111.554	391					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	8.526	10	.853	2.351	.011	R	S
	Within Groups	135.987	375	.363				
	Total	144.512	385					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	6.554	10	.655	2.762	.003	R	S
	Within Groups	90.404	381	.237				
	Total	96.959	391					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	2.581	10	.258	1.339	.208	FR	NS
	Within Groups	73.453	381	.193				
	Total	76.034	391					
Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	3.015	10	.302	1.164	.314	FR	NS
	Within Groups	97.370	376	.259				
	Total	100.386	386					
Simple Living	Between Groups	5.468	10	.547	1.652	.090	FR	NS
	Within Groups	125.802	380	.331				
	Total	131.270	390					

Sig. < 0.05 R S Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

Table 20 presents the significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of length of service.

It was shown in the table that there is no significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest and professionalism in terms of length of service since the computed p-value of .644 and .243 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. In terms of justness and sincerity, there is a significant difference since the p-value of .009 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. With respect to political neutrality, values responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of length of service, there is no significant differences in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents since the p-values of .222, .125, .481, .662, and .664 respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence with respect to justness and sincerity, the hypothesis is rejected while with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, rejected political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 20 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Municipal Employees with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Length of Service

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	H _o	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	.501	4	.125	.627	.644	FR	NS
	Within Groups	62.995	315	.200				
	Total	63.496	319					
Professionalism	Between Groups	.932	4	.233	1.374	.243	FR	NS
	Within Groups	53.546	316	.169				
	Total	54.477	320					
Justness and Sincerity	Between Groups	2.291	4	.573	3.414	.009	R	S
	Within Groups	52.853	315	.168				
	Total	55.144	319					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	1.262	4	.316	1.436	.222	FR	NS
	Within Groups	67.914	309	.220				
	Total	69.176	313					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	1.233	4	.308	1.821	.125	FR	NS
	Within Groups	53.337	315	.169				
	Total	54.570	319					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	.597	4	.149	.871	.481	FR	NS
	Within Groups	53.969	315	.171				
	Total	54.566	319					
Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	.519	4	.130	.601	.662	FR	NS
	Within Groups	67.151	311	.216				
	Total	67.670	315					
Simple Living	Between Groups	.539	4	.135	.598	.664	FR	NS
	Within Groups	70.743	314	.225				
	Total	71.282	318					

Sig. < 0.05 R S

Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

Ethics in public administration has been a subject of growing interest for both researchers and practitioners interested in the future of governance. This study examined the relationship between ethics and performance in local governance. We tested the effects over time of an ethics program on employees' perceptions (awareness of the code of ethics, ethical leadership, inclusion of employees in ethical decision making [EDM], ethical climate [EC], organizational commitment, and quality of work life [QWL]) and behavior (organizational citizenship behavior) in one Israeli regional council. We conducted a longitudinal study of 108 employees, using data from a two-phase survey (before implementation of the ethics program and a year after) and objective assessments of employees' behavior through managers' evaluations. The main findings show that the ethics program was very effective, resulting in greater awareness of the code of ethics, increased inclusion of employees in EDM, and an improved EC. Furthermore, ethical leadership was positively related to employees' awareness of the code of ethics, increased inclusion of employees in EDM, an improvement in the EC, greater organizational commitment, and higher QWL. Implications and suggestions for future studies are discussed.

Table 21 Significant Difference in the Subscription of RA 6713 as Assessed by the Respondents with respect to the Cited Variables in terms of Category

	SV	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	Ho	VI
Commitment to Public Interest	Between Groups	8.016	1	8.016	32.764	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	104.707	428	.245				
	Total	112.722	429					
Professionalism	Between Groups	14.856	1	14.856	71.210	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	89.497	429	.209				
	Total	104.353	430					
Justness and Sincerity	Between Groups	20.529	1	20.529	87.008	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	100.984	428	.236				
	Total	121.513	429					
Political Neutrality	Between Groups	28.038	1	28.038	92.575	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	127.812	422	.303				
	Total	155.851	423					
Responsiveness	Between Groups	15.120	1	15.120	70.235	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	92.140	428	.215				
	Total	107.260	429					
Nationalism and Patriotism	Between Groups	5.171	1	5.171	26.964	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	82.086	428	.192				
	Total	87.257	429					
Commitment to Democracy	Between Groups	7.752	1	7.752	31.107	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	105.415	423	.249				
	Total	113.167	424					
Simple Living	Between Groups	16.562	1	16.562	56.740	.000	R	S
	Within Groups	124.641	427	.292				
	Total	141.204	428					

Sig. < 0.05 R S

Sig. > 0.05 FR NS

Table 21 presents the significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of category.

The table revealed that there is a significant difference in the practice of RA 6713 as assessed by the respondents with respect to commitment to public interest, professionalism, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, commitment to democracy, and simple living in terms of category since the computed p-values are all .000 and are less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected

In the study of Aranas, 2016, it was discussed that the Ethical conduct of public servants is reinforced by political commitment. This political commitment, difficult to benchmark, had been demonstrated by some policies and pronouncements. It is essential to the proper conduct and operation of government that public officials be

independent and impartial and that public office not be used for private gain other than the remuneration provided by law. The public interest, therefore, requires that the law protect against any conflict of interest and establish standards for the conduct of elected officials and government employees in situations where conflicts may exist.

Table 22 Problems Encountered by Employees in the Subscription to RA 6713

Problems Encountered	F	%	Rank
With the bulk of work, I am forced to leave my work station	32	8.6	9
No specific or clear checklist designed by the agency to require from our clientele for every transaction	22	5.9	10
The irregular presence of signatories causes delay on the release of requested documents	76	20.5	2
The attitude like aggressiveness of clients forced the employees to use foul language	38	10.3	8
The culture of family ties favors any relative	59	15.9	3
Favoritism resulted to low motivation and loss of job satisfaction	56	15.1	4
Undefined guidelines or policy from the top officials affects the delivery of basic services	53	14.3	5
The limited budget and with the several rules and laws causes initiated projects to become non-sustainable	83	22.4	1
Loyalty to political parties affects the support or assistance to the clientele	43	11.6	7
There are instances of not properly disseminating information due to instructions of top officials	45	12.2	6

Table 22 on discloses the problems encountered by employees in the implantation of RA 6713.

The table revealed that the highest problems encountered by employees were the limited budget and the several rules and laws causing initiated projects to become non-sustainable with a frequency of 83 or 22.4 percent while the lowest frequency of 22 or 5.9 percent belongs to the problem of no specific or clear checklist designed by the agency to require from our clients for every transaction.

As stated by Whitton (2015) these related questions have been the subject of widespread research over the past two decades. Even so, in seeking to establish ethical standards and norms of professionalism, most public sector agencies today have scarcely advanced beyond the mechanism of the traditional rule-based Code of Conduct, often based on the 'core values' of the institution. Such rule-based Codes of Conduct generally aim to prohibit corruption and misconduct, rather than promoting ethical conduct in the exercise of public functions. This outlines the main issues behind these concerns, looks beyond to some of the reasons why traditional methods of managing ethical problems encountered by public officials often fail, and examines how this important deficit might be remedied.

Table 23 Problems Encountered by Stakeholders in the Subscription to RA 6713

Problems Encountered	f	%	Rank
Availability of official in the assigned unit	-	-	
Inaccurate requirements prior to the requested documents	12	19.7	7
Delayed release of requested documents	33	54.1	2
Using of harsh words when dealing with clients	10	16.4	8
Favors familiarity	43	70.5	1
The official concerned is not respectable	7	11.5	9
The steps given on the procedure for requesting assistance such as basic services are not clear	18	29.5	6
Programs and projects initiated are not sustainable	24	39.3	4
Assistance given depends on political affiliation	25	41.0	3
Information dissemination on public concern is not properly executed	20	32.8	5

Table 23 presents the problems encountered by stakeholders in the implementation of RA 6713.

The table revealed that the highest problem encountered by employees was the delayed release of requested documents with a frequency of 33 or 54.1 percent while the problem of the official concerned is not respectable and has the lowest frequency of 7 or 11.5 percent.

With the enumerated problems encountered by stakeholders, Derek C Bok, 2012, lamented in his article *Can Ethics be Taught?* that it will be difficult to make headway against these problems without a determined effort by the leaders of our national institutions. Regardless of the public is scarcely optimistic over the prospects, for society's faith in its leaders has declined precipitously in recent years.

FRAMEWORK ON THE GUIDELINES TO ADDRESS PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY RESPONDENTS

To guide employees in the scrutiny of subscription to RA 6713 otherwise known as the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees, a framework is hereby offered.

Among the problems considered by the employees is the limited budget, followed by the irregular presence of the signatories. Addressing irregular attendance in an

organizational setting necessitates a multifaceted approach that is both proactive and empathetic

On the other side, among stakeholders, the problems they have encountered include favors familiarity and delayed release of requested documents.

Whether it's a manager promoting a protege or a leader showing one employee undue favor, favoritism can erode employee morale and compromise the integrity of the workplace, perpetuating inequality and hindering the pursuit of a truly equitable professional environment. on the other hand, postponed document disclosure may result in legal issues, erode confidence, cause operational disruptions, affect people, and impede research. For successful governance and accountability, timeliness in transparency is essential.

ACTION PLAN

Rationale:

Activity	Objectives	Timeline	Sources of Funds	Key Performance Indicator
Employee Re-orientation on RA 6713	To have employees be prompted of their duties and responsibilities and be reminded of impartiality	Annual	LGU	95-100% of Municipal Employees were re-oriented of the provisions of RA 6713
Employee involvement in Department/Unit Budget Preparation and Accountability	To maximize the budget allocated to every department/unit	Annual	LGU	Executed Budget Allocation and Budget Execution
Orientation of ARTA Revisit of OPCR/IPCR Employee Engagement	To avoid procrastination in the processing of documents	Year-round	LGU	Accurate Individual Work Accomplishment Report

In the conduct and based on the results of the current study the following activities were hereby presented to guide municipal employees- not limited to permanent employees to augment gaps in the subscription of employees and officials in the

government sector. This action plan is offered upon identification of various factors that affect ethical and unethical behaviors in organizations, including a decision-maker's social, government and legal, work, professional, and personal environments.

The study's findings, as stated in Table 21 in particular. Due to the respondents' differing claims in each of the eight categories, this recommended action plan may widen the disparities between the two groups.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the data generated, the following conclusions were hereby drawn:

1. Stakeholders have different assessments compared to the responses of the employees on the areas of RA 6713 otherwise known as the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees.
 2. The assessment or rating of the Stakeholders illustrates that there is a need for a re-orientation, and reminds the employees of the provisions of RA 6713, particularly in the areas of Commitment to Public Interest, Professionalism, and, Commitment to Democracy.
 3. The majority of respondents who were stakeholders believed that familiarity is typically observed in the municipalities.
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Recommendations

The following are the recommendations of the researcher after a comprehensive analysis of the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. A re-orientation of the provision of RA 6713 should be offered to the employees to address the areas that were observed differently by the stakeholders.
 2. Since the two groups provided a different response on the four areas of RA 6713, it is recommended policies of the municipalities congruent to the Act may be revisited.
 3. Fairness and equality in serving people should be of utmost observance of public officials and employees.
 4. The same study may be replicated using different locale and respondents.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the conduct of this research authorities of the seven municipalities under survey were provided a letter of intent and approval from the Municipal Mayors through their respective Human Resource Management Officer. Further, the voluntary participation of

the respondents was solicited, moreover, compliance to RA 10173 (Data Privacy Act of 2012) was abided.

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